

ADSORPTION OF HYDROXYBENZENES BY SUGAR CHARCOAL DISCONTINUITIES IN THE ADSORPTION OF PHENOL, RESORCINOL, AND QUINOL FROM AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS

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Adsorption by sugar coal of phenol resorcinol and quinol from aqueous solutions have been studied.

In continuation of our previous work (Jain and Jha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 685), adsorption of hydroxybenzenes by sugar charcoal has been further studied.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The adsorption experiments were carried out by weighing exactly 0.5 g. of the charcoal in clean, dry, glass bottles similar in size to which 100 c.c. of each solution in freshly prepared distilled water was pipetted separately. The bottles were shaken for the same length of time and kept for about 24 hours, at the end of which interval the amount of solute was determined in the supernatant liquid by the bromine method (Redman, Weith and Brock. *J. Chem. Soc. Abst.*, 1913, I, 632) in the case of phenol, cresols (Chausser, *Chem. Zentr.*, 1900, II, 118), and resorcinol.

An approximately 0.1N brominating solution was prepared by dissolving 2.76 g. of potassium bromate and 15 g. of potassium bromide in water, and making up the solution to one litre. The brominating solution was standardised by means of a standard sodium thiosulphate solution.

15. C.c. of each of the solutions of the said substances (about 0.1N), were placed in a stoppered bottle together with 50 c.c. of water and 5 c.c. of HCl (*d* 1.2); the brominating solution was now run in from a burette and the bottle shaken continuously until a slight yellow colour was permanent. The bottle was stoppered and after shaking for 1 minute. 0.5 c.c. of a 20% solution of potassium iodide was added, the mixture shaken for another minute and the iodine titrated with standard thiosulphate solution.

Estimation of Quinol.—The supernatant liquid of quinol was titrated with iodine according to the method of Kolthoff (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1926, 45, 745). 0.4 c.c. of 4N-acetic acid, about 8 c.c. of 2N sodium acetate, and an excess of standard iodine solution were added to 10 c.c. of about 0.1N-quinol solution and the mixture was titrated back with standard sodium thiosulphate. A 0.0001N solution can thus be titrated to 1%.

Blank experiments were run side by side to determine the original concentration (C_2). Determination with charcoal gave the equilibrium

concentration. The amount of adsorption (X) was determined by difference ($C_0 - C_e$) from 100 c.c. of the aqueous solution. Equilibrium concentrations were calculated in millimoles per litre.

R E S U L T S.

The results for the adsorption of phenol and cresols are recorded in Table I, while that of dihydroxybenzenes in Table II, and in Fig. 1.

TABLE I.

Adsorption by 0.5 g. sugar charcoal from 100 c.c. of aqueous solutions.

Phenol.					
C_0 .	C_e .	X .	X/m .	$\text{Log } C_e$.	$\text{Log } X/m$.
0.4414	0.3853	0.0561	0.1122	$\bar{1}.5858$	$\bar{1}.0500$
0.4193	0.3604	0.0589	0.1178	$\bar{1}.5568$	$\bar{1}.0712$
0.3972	0.3382	0.0590	0.1180	$\bar{1}.5292$	$\bar{1}.0719$
0.3752	0.3137	0.0615	0.1230	$\bar{1}.4965$	$\bar{1}.0899$
0.3531	0.2946	0.0585	0.1170	$\bar{1}.4692$	$\bar{1}.0682$
0.3310	0.2721	0.0589	0.1178	$\bar{1}.4348$	$\bar{1}.0712$
0.3090	0.2485	0.0605	0.1210	$\bar{1}.3954$	$\bar{1}.0828$
0.2870	0.2275	0.0595	0.1190	$\bar{1}.3570$	$\bar{1}.0755$
0.2439	0.1841	0.0598	0.1196	$\bar{1}.2650$	$\bar{1}.0778$
0.2252	0.1638	0.0614	0.1228	$\bar{1}.2144$	$\bar{1}.0892$
0.2139	0.1534	0.0605	0.1210	$\bar{1}.1858$	$\bar{1}.0828$
0.2026	0.1381	0.0645	0.1290	$\bar{1}.1402$	$\bar{1}.1106$
0.1914	0.1345	0.0569	0.1138	$\bar{1}.1287$	$\bar{1}.0561$
0.1813	0.1238	0.0575	0.1150	$\bar{1}.0927$	$\bar{1}.0607$
0.1689	0.1143	0.0546	0.1092	$\bar{1}.0581$	$\bar{1}.0382$
0.1576	0.1041	0.0535	0.1070	$\bar{1}.0175$	$\bar{1}.0294$
0.1464	0.0947	0.0517	0.1034	$\bar{2}.9763$	$\bar{1}.0145$
<i>p</i> -Cresol.					
0.3742	0.3541	0.0201	0.0402	$\bar{1}.5491$	$\bar{2}.6042$
0.3555	0.3344	0.0211	0.0422	$\bar{1}.5242$	$\bar{2}.6253$
0.3368	0.3148	0.0220	0.0440	$\bar{1}.4980$	$\bar{2}.6435$
0.3181	0.2949	0.0232	0.0464	$\bar{1}.4696$	$\bar{2}.6665$
0.2994	0.2756	0.0238	0.0476	$\bar{1}.4402$	$\bar{2}.6776$
0.2806	0.2556	0.0250	0.0500	$\bar{1}.4076$	$\bar{2}.6990$

TABLE I (contd.).

<i>m</i> -Cresol.					
C_0	C_e	X	X/m	$\text{Log } C_e$	$\text{Log } X/m$
0'4131	0'3891	0'0240	0'0480	1'5900	$\bar{2}$ '6912
0'3925	0'3674	0'0251	0'0502	$\bar{1}$ '5652	$\bar{2}$ '7007
0'3721	0'3467	0'0254	0'0508	1'5400	$\bar{2}$ '7059
0'3515	0'3255	0'0260	0'0520	1'5126	$\bar{2}$ '7160
0'3309	0'3034	0'0265	0'0530	$\bar{1}$ '4820	$\bar{2}$ '7243
0'3103	0'2830	0'0273	0'0546	$\bar{1}$ '4518	$\bar{2}$ '7372
<i>o</i> -Cresol					
0'4093	0'3813	0'0290	0'0560	$\bar{1}$ '5812	$\bar{2}$ '7481
0'3780	0'3481	0'0299	0'0598	$\bar{1}$ '5414	$\bar{2}$ '7767
0'3522	0'3213	0'0309	0'0618	$\bar{1}$ '5073	$\bar{2}$ '7910
0'3284	0'2971	0'0313	0'0626	$\bar{1}$ '4729	$\bar{2}$ '7966
0'3045	0'2721	0'0324	0'0648	$\bar{1}$ '4348	$\bar{2}$ '8116
0'2826	0'2498	0'0328	0'0656	$\bar{1}$ '4076	$\bar{2}$ '8169

TABLE II.

Dihydroxybenzenes.

Adsorption of dihydroxybenzenes by 0'5 g. charcoal from 100 c.c. aqueous solution.

Hydroquinone.					
C_0	C_e	X	X/m	$\text{Log } C_e$	$\text{Log } X/m$
0'2740	0'2550	0'0190	0'0380	$\bar{1}$ '4065	$\bar{2}$ '5798
0'2603	0'2364	0'0239	0'0478	$\bar{1}$ '3736	$\bar{2}$ '6794
0'2466	0'2249	0'0217	0'0434	$\bar{1}$ '3521	$\bar{2}$ '6375
0'2329	0'2112	0'0217	0'0434	$\bar{1}$ '3247	$\bar{2}$ '6375
0'2192	0'1977	0'0215	0'0430	$\bar{1}$ '2960	$\bar{2}$ '6335
0'2055	0'1805	0'0250	0'0500	$\bar{1}$ '2565	$\bar{2}$ '6990
0'1918	0'1662	0'0256	0'0512	$\bar{1}$ '2206	$\bar{2}$ '7093
0'1781	0'1533	0'0248	0'0496	$\bar{1}$ '1856	$\bar{2}$ '6955

TABLE II (contd.).

Resorcinol.					
C_e	C_a	X	X/m	$\bar{\text{Log}} C_e$	$\bar{\text{Log}} X/m$
0.2777	0.2573	0.0204	0.0408	1.4104	2.6107
0.2639	0.2421	0.0218	0.0436	1.3840	2.6395
0.2501	0.2293	0.0208	0.0416	1.3604	2.6191
0.2363	0.2120	0.0243	0.0486	1.3263	2.6866
0.2294	0.2060	0.0234	0.0468	1.3139	2.6702
0.2225	0.2020	0.0205	0.0410	1.3054	2.6128
0.2165	0.1950	0.0215	0.0430	1.2900	2.6335
0.2087	0.1861	0.0226	0.0452	1.2697	2.6551

Table III shows that the adsorption isotherms of the following substances are of somewhat periodic type.

FIG. I.

Curves 1-6 refer respectively to phenol
o-cresol, *m*-cresol, *p*-cresol, resorcinol
 and quinol.

TABLE III.

Molar conc. at the max. and min. points on the curve.	Diff. bet. two max. & min. pts.	Molar conc. at the max. & min. points on the curve.	Diff. bet. two max. and min. pts.	Molar conc. at the max. and min. points on the curve	Diff. between two max and min. pts
Phenol.			Quinol.		
0'00409	—	0'00243	0'00021	0'00231	
0'00382	0'00027	0'00201	0'00042	0'00214	0'00017
0'00361	0'00021	0'00174	0'00027	0'00180	0'00034
0'00334	0'00027	0'00163	0'00011	0'00151	0'00029
Resorcinol.					
0'00313	0'00021	0'00146	0'00017	0'00234	
0'00291	0'00022	0'00143	0'00003	0'00220	0'00014
0'00264	0'00027	0'00122	0'00021	0'00192	0'00028
				0'00177	0'00015
				0'00170	0'00007

Chaplin (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, 32, 909) studied the adsorption of aqueous phenol on charcoal and obtained discontinuous curves with rectangular steps. Kolthoff and van der Goot (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1929, 48, 265, 287) found that in the adsorption of hydroxybenzenes on charcoal Freundlich adsorption equation could be satisfactorily applied to the results.

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